

CIVIL SOCIETY: ASPECTS OF GLOBALIZATION

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ORCID:0000-0001-8106-1355***ABSTRACT**

Under the influence of globalization, civil society is expanding, transnational communities, global movements, international scientific and professional associations are being formed, and so on. In other words, a unique public space is being formed, basic common rights are being improved, and attempts are being made to prevent global threats without the participation of states. This study is due to general socio-cultural changes that occur both in the national and global space. Finally, during the period of increasing globalization and complexity of social ties, the question of the place and role of civil society and its institutions in modern society is becoming more relevant. Globalization, on the one hand, promotes the dissemination of ideas of civil society through international networks and platforms of cooperation, and on the other - poses new challenges and threats associated with the growing influence of multinational corporations and the decline in the level of democracy in the world. Therefore, it is important that civil society is active, united and able to mobilize society to solve common problems, in particular in a globalized world.

Keywords: globalization, global civil society, global crisis, culture, society, democracy, state, law, values.

Globalization defines the process of uniting all of humanity on planet Earth. It is the planetary level that defines the process of "globality". There is a unification of human activity, the development of international trade, the flow of capital between countries increases, access to foreign resources, including labor markets opens up, and there are general trends of integration in the socio-cultural and economic context. This convergence contributes to increased interaction, integration, and interdependence between nations.

In E. Cassirer's philosophy, globalization can be understood as a symbolic form that functions as a worldview in modern discourses. Globalization as a symbolic form has become an image of the world, its image, it has changed our understanding of space and time. In the framework of World-Systems Analysis, capitalism is presented as a historical and social system that integrates its achievements into the "world-economy", and it is the methods of modern capitalism that have allowed the modern world economy to go beyond the political borders of individual countries.

Against the background of globalization processes in the mass consciousness and public opinion, a contradiction is formed, represented by rational optimism, which gave rise to civilization, and on the other hand, caused a crisis (existential, environmental, economic). The process of globalization has an ontological dimension. This is, first of all, the process of expanding the boundaries of reality. From the point of view of instrumentalism and pragmatism, it is science, education and democracy that can help to go beyond the temporal and spatial contours of human activity. The philosophy of technology pays attention to the scientific and technological revolution that catalyzed the process of globalization. Globalization generates a complex of acute socio-cultural contradictions and requires adequate understanding and research, which can be fruitfully

carried out within the framework of philosophical analysis, which in itself has a high level of systemic generalization.

This leads to the actualization of the idea of civil society and its substantive discussion, and also allows us to raise the question of its philosophical and legal foundations in a different way.

The problem of understanding the content, patterns of formation and development of civil society from the "Hegelian" time to the present day is constantly at the center of philosophical, socio-political and legal scientific discourse. Now this issue is becoming increasingly relevant. As the British publicist Edward Lucas rightly argues, in the third millennium, civil society gains recognition of an element of a solid foundation of a political system, even more significant than free elections, as it generates the phenomenon of "civic responsibility".

Civil society plays a special role in transition societies. This is clearly evidenced by the events of 2014 in Ukraine, when civil society acted as the driving force and decisive political entity that led to the beginning of revolutionary actions and the final overthrow of the criminal regime. Tragic events have shown that the practice of developing Ukrainian civil society significantly outstrips its scientific understanding and interpretation, even despite numerous scientific works published since the independence of Ukraine.

It is worth noting that global civil society is an extremely controversial political institution regarding the possibility of full implementation, so it is worth determining how realistic the prospect of effective implementation of global civil society in the contradictory realities of cultural diversity, interweaving of interethnic interests, a large number of uncertainties in all spheres of life and other factors is in general.

I. Kant also allowed the emergence of the right of World citizenship, which unites citizens and the state in the Commonwealth of states ("universal civil society"). Since then, researchers have been debating the subject of global (global, universal, international, mega-society, etc.) society, even arguing about its name.

Today, global civil society as a political institution is not sufficiently conceptualized; the reason for this may be the multidimensional nature of globalization processes, their contradictions at the national and transnational levels.

Civil society is formed "at different speeds", depending on historical, cultural and economic conditions. V. Buryak notes that "the political and cultural metaphors" West "and" East," North "and" South "grasp the fundamental differences between the regions of the world. Their differences have developed over thousands of years, and historical, cultural, economic, and political features affect the pace and direction of civic initiatives." Global civil society is not so "global", because it manifests itself unevenly on different continents. Global transformations both occurred and are still occurring unevenly today [2; p. 44].

Despite the obvious amorphous nature of such a "motley" formation, the real disunity of civil societies on a global scale, the obvious Mosaic and lack of consistency, J. R. R. Tolkien and others. Kane in "global civil society?" [5; p.77], insists that it is possible to state the existence of a certain supranational specific civil entity (the researcher calls it "society of societies" – "Society of societies"). Openness, the movement towards expanding democracy, and the desire for universal (universal) values are its distinctive characteristics.

Let's identify the main advantages of a global civil society that can contribute to its evolution, and those factors that positively affect this process.:

1) in recent decades, various global crises have been rapidly spreading, which cause the emergence of common interests and can produce an awareness of a single identity among all Earthlings;

2) building a global community that will act on the principles of a supranational political space, potentially, if not contribute to solving global problems, then at least mitigate their consequences;

3) the nature of global problems leads to the emergence of social actors who require international collective management of these problems not only by national governments and governmental international organizations. Some globally important decisions (e.g. biosphere protection, non-proliferation and non-use of nuclear weapons) require concerted action at the global level;

4) the design and effective functioning of a global civil society is made possible by people's interest in ensuring personal and Planetary Security;

5) the global format of civil society can also be considered as an integral part of globalization transformations that can no longer be stopped. Some researchers interpret global civil society as a reaction to globalization;

6) the existence of a global civil society can lead to the erasure of national borders through the emergence of so-called "World citizenship" with equal

rights and freedoms for all. This is quite a fantastic dream, which was talked about by the Greeks of the Hellenistic era, but humanity for more than two millennia has not come close to such a format on a global scale;

7) The Information Society is rapidly evolving, new, inexpensive ways of cross-border communication are emerging, and the role of the internet in the daily life of society has increased. Virtual communication skills (communication activities) have become a necessity. Each member of the network has the opportunity to communicate with a large number of people, influence them, and mobilize them. Virtual communication eliminates the problem of inequality that exists in mass communication between the elite and the mass, because in virtual communication everyone is equal [4; p. 166]; 8) the development of the above-mentioned horizontal links in global communication contributes to the formation of a clear socio-political position, affects the ability to quickly organize and mobilize – to take active actions to protect their own or collective interests;

9) thanks to the global civic cooperation of non-state actors, it is possible to create a single database of proposals and criticism on certain situations, recommendations for decision-making and possible ways to implement them;

10) "others" disappear as a characteristic of the global social system of the future (the approach of the Russian sociologist T. Tsymbal) [3; p. 171].

At the same time, many scientists are of the opinion that it is impossible to build a global civil society. The creation of this type of social education is very often considered utopian theories, and a number of arguments are given to confirm such a pessimistic hypothesis.

Let's try to highlight the main reservations about the realism of building a global civil society and outline the main obstacles to its development. First of all, modern man is characterized by the lack of a global way of thinking, it is narrowly focused on local problems. In the global civic dimension, a small, local entity is leveled, and the prerogative is a large organism. As a result, the identity and individuality of a certain territory (s) is devalued. There is an imposition of alien, uncharacteristic principles of governance, dictating the rules of the game, and imposing alien models of political (and not only) culture. The values of each community differ and depend on many factors; it is not possible to form single acceptable values for a single earthly society, because each nation has its own priorities and beliefs; the dialogue of cultures is complicated, cross-cultural interaction does not have a common support [4; p. 166].

Another problematic point is the existence of different cultural Poles, sometimes categorical unwillingness to accept a different, culturally different side (international terrorism, religious extremism and other manifestations). Let us also pay attention to such obstacles as the lack of education of a large part of Earthlings, the income gap, unequal access to social, economic, and educational services, and other social problems that naturally generate different interests of the peoples of the planet.

The cultural revival of many nations contributes to focusing on their own heritage and maintaining national traditions. This comes into conflict with the desire for some unification of Earthlings in order to implement the tasks of global civil society.

Although the formation of a global civil society has been made possible by modern information technologies that erase borders, but with the continuous growth of opportunities for the transmission and exchange of information, the problem of digital inequality – differences in citizens' access to social, economic, educational, cultural and other services through information and Communication Technologies-is becoming more acute. This is another obstacle to approaching the implementation of the global civil society development project.

With a huge gap in the social indicators of the world's countries and cultural differences between peoples, we observe the indifference of some countries (developed economies) to the problems of others (especially developing countries).

In our opinion, the implementation of global civil society projects implies reformist development of countries, but not all countries are ready for reforms. Many of them, at their level of development, are not familiar with the mechanisms of reform; national systems are not ready to adapt to global requirements. In order to unite into one global civil society, people need to receive objective information about the state of affairs, which is impossible due to the conduct of aggressive information wars in the modern world.

In the context of the outlined characteristics of the process of possible evolution of global civil society, we recall the approach of the German researcher A. Klein, who identifies three models of international politics (real, international and cosmopolitan). If the real model is based on the unlimited sovereignty of national states, non – governmental public organizations perform an advisory function, the international model already recognizes the great influence of international organizations and non-governmental public organizations, then the cosmopolitan model assigns the subjects of global civil society, in particular non-governmental public organizations, the role of actors of international civil society who challenge the political dominance of national states [5; p. 133].

Most researchers are inclined to the real model, sceptically assessing the possibility of influence of non-governmental public organizations: 1) the independence of non-governmental public organizations as social or political actors is questioned; 2) non-governmental public organizations are very diverse in nature, which complicates interaction (emancipated, conservative, progressive, authoritarian, neoliberal, etc.). Therefore, it is reasonable to think that we have rather a heterogeneous set of individual actors and an “internationalized, but not international civil society.”

At the same time, scientists-” optimists ” are of the opinion that in the future, international non-governmental organizations can form a global civil society that will influence the system of international political and socio-economic relations no less significantly than within national borders, civil society affects the policy

of the state. So, we can state that an important feature of modern globalization trends is the significant development of non-governmental (public) relations at the international level.

The formation of a global civil society, in our opinion, is the result of drawing a format of a globalized world – a specific, modern world transformed by the influence of globalization. A globalized world is: 1) the merger of national economies into a single global system based on the ease of capital movement; 2) information openness of the world, rapid technological renewal; 3) liberalization of the movement of goods and capital; 4) planetary scientific revolution based on communication convergence; 5) interethnic social movements; 6) international education, etc.

On the other hand, the formation of a global civil society, in our opinion, is a response to the global crisis as a comprehensive phenomenon that affects the vital interests of all peoples and countries of the world, generated by the General Laws of the existence and development of mankind. Political, economic, social, ethnic, demographic, environmental and other contradictions are becoming more acute; the means used to achieve goals are already ineffective, resulting in unforeseen situations and problems. The global crisis most clearly reveals the present as a period of instability or a state when serious changes are approaching. Today, humanity is experiencing a crisis that is systemic, general civilizational.

Thus, globalization has a significant impact on the current situation in the world. It promotes the rapid dissemination of Information, Technologies, goods and services, enabling countries to interact and collaborate. However, it is worth noting that civil society in the world of globalization and modernity faces a number of problems. Current challenges such as climate change, cybersecurity, and others are also putting civil society at risk. Globalization leads to increased inequality between countries, loss of cultural identity and dependence of economies on each other. To solve these problems, active participation of citizens in the processes of governance and development of civil society is necessary. Preserving cultural heritage, supporting civic initiatives, and promoting mutual understanding between nations will help strengthen civil society in the face of globalization and the challenges of our time. To be successful in the context of globalization, countries need to develop their competitive advantages, limit the negative aspects of globalization, and promote cooperation to solve common problems.

Global civil society has a perspective of formation, provided that it is focused on solving security, economic, social, demographic and other problems of the world's countries, and forming a global public policy.

The imperative of the modern era should be an awareness of the commonality of human civilization on our planet. Humanity is united, as are its problems and patterns of development. Since it is impossible to overcome the global crisis by one state or nation, we need cooperation on a global scale and close constructive cooperation both at the state and non-state levels (within civil society).

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